

PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT AND BUDGET EVALUATION AS A POLITICAL INSTRUMENT IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the work is to ascertain the role of budget as a political instrument in the Nigerian federal setting in which there is recurring vertical and horizontal conflicts over resource sharing. To effectively address issues raised in this paper, the pawpaw and pineapple theories were adopted. Data was drawn from both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources were observation and questionnaire, while secondary sources were text books, journals and government documents. Collected data was evaluated with the aid of Almonds structural- functional theory, as well as simple percentage statistical equation measures and tables. The major finding was that budget represented a very strong political tool which could be effectively utilized to ameliorate the tensions surrounding resource allocation in Nigeria. Secondly, the executive organ has not adopted the necessary conscious efforts towards addressing observations and demands from various quarters over denials of equitable share in resource sharing in the country. On the basis of the findings, the following recommendations were made: One; the government must make every necessary effort to reflect the principles of equity and equality in the country's resource sharing measures. Two; there should be a deliberate policy efforts by the federal government in addressing the perceived and factual skews in resource sharing in the country. Three; the government has to appreciate and elevate the instrument of budget as a strong political instrument that would redress observed short coming in the country's resource sharing formula or system.

Keywords: budget; fiscal federalism; equity and equality; resource sharing; politics.

INTRODUCTION

Budget remains a very important policy or political instrument in the hand of government (Udoh 2022; Udoh 2024, Udoh. and Madueke, 2018). The role of budget in shaping a country's resource allocation is very vital, especially in a federation like Nigeria with history of persistent vertical and horizontal antagonism arising mostly from disagreements among the federating units against prevailing resource, especially revenue, sharing method. The recurring antagonism has ensured that Nigeria remained a country on

the brink of disintegration. Between 1962, just two years into the country's independence, and 1966, the country was embroiled in a number of political crises. These included census crisis, revenue allocation disagreement, and contention over creation of new regions for minorities, election crisis, military incursion into governance and genocide against Igbo people residing in the northern part of the country (Dudley, 1982; Okoli, 1980; Ikejiani, 1988; Uwechue, 1979; Madiebo, 1980). These crises culminated in a civil war that lasted three years, 1967 and 1970, which pitched the federal government against the people of the Eastern region (Uwechue: 1979).

At the end of the war, General Yakubu Gowon's led federal military government policy of Reconciliation, Conciliation and Rehabilitation appeared to have assuaged the Igbo's of the eastern region by assuring them of reintegration into the Nigerian polity (Shillington: 2005; Encyclopedia, 2006). This policy and subsequent similar policies that targeted the interest of other ethnic groups by different governments at different times had appeared to guarantee the emergence of a stable and progressive Nigerian polity. This has, however, been punctured by recent resurgence of strong centrifugal forces in the country, seen in the emergence of several militant groups, among which are; the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), the Niger Delta Avengers, Niger Delta Suicide Squad, and Joint Niger Delta Front which are agitating for the institution of Niger Delta Republic; the Boko Haram insurgents based in the northern part of the country which has the goal of dismembering the country on basis of Muslim doctrine; and the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) which has resuscitated the demand by the Igbo's for the establishment of an Independent Republic of Biafra for the Igbo extraction.

All the agitations are to a great extent, products of resentment among the federating units and ethnic groups against the prevailing resource sharing in the country which has favoured some segments while leaving others unsatisfied. While there are broader calls for the restructuring of the country's federal system, there has also been an understanding that there is the possibility for the use of the instrument of budget in reallocating resources, which would generate equity and stability in the country. The contention has raised strong discourses on nature of resource sharing in the country, and has brought up the question of necessity and possibility of the application of the instrument of budget as a political tool that would close the gaps created by prevalent resource sharing formula and subsequently, douse the disintegrative forces and create a stable and progressive Nigeria.

The contention over revenue allocation has remained a central factor in the raging demand for the restructuring of Nigeria's federal system. "It is characterized by constant struggle, clamour for change, and very recently, violence in the form of resource control in the Niger delta" (Arowolo, 2011 (Quoted in Ewetan, 2012: p.9). The component units were discontented with the pattern of revenue distribution between the central government and the component governments. The clamour for fiscal restructuring has pushed two concepts, 'resource control and sovereign national conference', to the forefront of most popular lexicons in recent discourses about Nigerian government and politics. Some scholars have drawn attention to the nature of federalism as it is currently practiced in Nigeria, raising questions that border on the efficacy or otherwise of prevailing federal structure in enhancing political integration and socio-economic development of the country (Ojo, 2009; Elaigwu, 1998; Ayoade, 1988; Osaghae, 1978). The contention is that the prevailing fiscal and political federal structures have stunted national development by arousing disintegrative feelings among the constituent units and ethnic groups. There is a near general agreement among

scholars that the federal system, when placed on a comparative scale with the unitary and con-federal systems, is the best for organizing a vast area with radically diverse cultures as Nigeria is. The contention, therefore, is on the nature of prevailing resource allocation system.

Among canvassed solutions was a call for convocation of a sovereign national conference and institution of policy of resource control which would address discontent from various quarters. The expectation is that this move would douse the spirit of agitation among various groups in the polity and establish a stable environment conducive for national development. The issues raised above have led to a number of pertinent questions. One; is the federal system the most advantageous system for organizing the Nigerian society? Two; what specific changes in resource sharing would enable the country generate functional and progressive fiscal federal structure? Three; what actions have the government adopted in the past and what impact have government actions made on the generation of functional fiscal structure in Nigeria. Four; has the Nigerian government made any efforts at applying the instrument of budget as a political tool towards addressing the challenges in resource sharing? Five; will the application of the instrument of budget as a political tool aid in stemming the challenge of resource sharing in the country?. This paper represents an attempt directed at addressing the critical condition that Nigeria is passing through with a focus on unraveling the possibilities of applying the instrument of budget towards moderating resource allocation in the country and stemming the tide of disintegration which the country face.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual review

Federalism: This is one of the systems of organizing the state or society. It is characterized by the fundamental factor of constitutional sharing of state powers between a central government and constituent governments. Federalism describes; “the distribution of the force of the state among a number of coordinate bodies each originating in and controlled by the constitution” (Dicey, in Ray 2004:150). Expressed in a very simplistic manner, federalism is an “association of states that form a new one” (Hamilton, in Ray 2004:151). A federal state could originate either through the process of aggregation or devolution. In aggregation, some erstwhile independent states, for security, economic or other reasons, pool their resources together and form a new state with a common central government whose powers is guaranteed by the constitution. In devolution, an existing central government for administrative convenience or other reasons may transfer some of the governmental powers to component units whose share of powers is constitutionally guaranteed. The common index is the constitutional guarantee of the powers associated with each level of government. To ensure adherence to the stipulated division of powers provision is made for a written constitution and an apex court called the Supreme Court. The Supreme Court interprets the constitutional provisions when disagreements arise. The United States of America was the first country to adopt the federalism system of organizing the society.

National Integration: National integration is that condition in which citizens of a given country consciously overcome ethnic, religious, language and other differences to generate a sense of oneness among them. It arises from the acknowledgement and acceptance of the existence of a common identity by the citizens. Duverger (In Ojo, 2009), viewed national

integration as “the process of unifying a society which tends to make it a harmonious city, based upon an order its members regard as equitably harmonious.” Jacob & Tenue (In Ojo, 2009) see national integration as “a relationship of community among people within the same political entity... a state of mind or disposition to be cohesive, to act together to be committed to mutual programmes”. To Morrison et al. (In Ojo, 2009) national integration is “A process by which members of a social system develop linkages and location so that the boundaries of the system persist over time and the boundaries of sub-systems become less consequential in affecting behaviour. In this process members of the social system develop an escalating sequence of contact, cooperation, consensus and community”. The importance of national integration lies in the fact that it constitutes a necessary condition for effective pursuit and attainment of political stability and sustainable socio-economic advancement.

Fiscal Federalism: This refers to a system of managing the distribution of revenue and expenditure in a federation. It implies the existence of more than one level of government in a country, with each level accorded expenditure responsibilities and taxing powers (Okigbo, 1965, in Anyanwu, 1997). Fiscal federal system in a country perform the function of specifying which areas of sources of revenue (tax and others) and governmental functions are assigned to each level of government in a federal arrangement. Fiscal federalism is necessary because each level of government is, within the bounds of the constitution, a sovereign unit within the federation (Herbert, 1979, in Anyanwu, 1997).

Budget: This is the documentation of government expected revenue and expenditure over a given period, mostly a year. It represents government's plan of action over a given time.

Empirical Review

What are the factors that have entrenched agitations by ethnic groups and constituents against prevailing resource sharing in the country? Scholars have emphasized the heterogeneous cultural and religious background of the country. In his analysis of the emergence of Nigeria, Barro (1991) observed that: “Nigeria gained her independence as an amalgamated country of various independent and varied cultural divide (Benin Kingdom, (Midwest region) Oyo empire (Yoruba, western region), Hausa-Fulani empires (Northern region) and Igbo cultural groupings (Eastern region), from its colonial lord (Britain) in 1960”. Using the submissions made by various ethnic groups to the Human Rights Violations Investigation Commission (HRVIC) that was set up in Nigeria in 1999 as indicator, Mustapha (2004) notes that: “Nigeria is a country characterized by intense ethnic polarization and conflict”. Highlighting the divide among Nigerians, Afegbua (2000) contends that: “Nigeria, being a multi-religious and ethnic society, had experienced massive ethnic, sectional, religious and political violence that has led to grievous socio-economic and political consequences on the psyche of the nation”. Expressing the inherent danger in ethnic antagonism, Ojie and Ekwhrudjakpor (2009) noted that: "The ethnic conflicts are usually struggles and wars of subordination, rebellion and hegemony". Inherent in the views expressed above is the acknowledgment that colonialism created a multi-religious and ethnic Nigerian society. And that this condition has in turn engendered different problems, one of which is agitations by ethnic groups and constituent units for higher resource allocation. Each ethnic groups has consistently fought to draw as much of the national resource to itself. With regard to possible solution to the ethnic antagonism in Nigeria Ojie and Ekwhrudjakpor (2009) decried the concentration of power with the central government and posited that: “The practice of true federalism and resource control will not only reduce its (central government)

attraction but will re-channel the dissipated energies of the various federating units to resource creation”. Expressing agreement with Ojie and Ekwhrudjakpor, Mustapha (2004) observed that: “A reform of the federal system which returns substantial economic and political initiative to the states and zones will help to channel political energies into less destructive ways”.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Pawpaw and Pineapple Theory

The Pawpaw and pineapple theories were adopted in explaining issues in the work. The theories were generated by Unwana-Abasi Udoh (2023) in his bid to find a lasting solution to the incessant agitations among constituent units and ethnic groups in Nigeria over skewed resource sharing formula in the country. The major thesis of the theories is that a lasting solution is possible to the problem of agitations over revenue sharing in Nigeria if the national resource is viewed as ripened pawpaw or pineapple by relevant authorities. According to the theorist, the application of the pawpaw dimension would generate justice, equity and fairness, while the application of the pineapple dimension would generate shrewdness and equality. The application of the two theories in this work assisted in exposing the possibility of utilization of the instrument of budget as a political tool which could strongly reduce the level of disintegrative agitations in the country over resource sharing.

The application of the paw and pineapple theories brought forward the fact that while revenue sharing formula was a rigid document that required strict and rigorous procedure for it to be changed, the instrument of budget was more flexible and periodic which presented it as a very functional tool for adjusting government allocation policies regularly. Thus, the theories served the important utility of highlighting the very important role of budget as an instrument of stabilization through the adjustment and moderation of skewed existing resource sharing system, without waiting until the existing resource sharing law was amended or changed.

Indeed, the application of the paw paw and pineapple theories exposed the fact that a conscious and deliberate focus by the government on budget as a political tool would present the government with a portent but more accessible and flexible means of addressing agitations against perceived and real deprivations arising from prevailing resource sharing system in the country.

METHODOLOGY

The work is a survey research, and adopts both qualitative and quantitative methods of data generation. The work applied both primary and secondary data. The methods of observation and questionnaire were adopted for the purpose of generating primary data, while secondary data was generated by consulting academic works, including textbooks, journals and government documents. The questionnaires consisted of closed ended questions with provision for alternative specific responses which aided in the evaluation of research questions.

The simple percentage statistical equation and tables for the grouping and assessment of data collected was adopted.

FINDINGS

Questionnaire responses

Question one: Are you conversant with the utilities of budget?

Options	Frequency	Percentage score
YES	115	95.83%
NO	5	4.17%
TOTAL	120	100

Question two: Do you consider budget a strong political tool in government?

Options	Frequency	Percentage score
YES	116	96.67%
NO	4	3.33%
TOTAL	120	100%

Question three: Can budget serve as political instrument of redistribution of societal resources?

Options	Frequency	Percentage score
YES	108	90%
NO	14	10%
TOTAL	120	100%

Question four: Have Nigerian governments adequately applied of the instrument of budget as an effective political tool of resource redistribution in the country?

Options	Frequency	Percentage score
YES	32	26.67%
NO	88	73.33%
TOTAL	120	100%

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Interpretation of Response to Question One

115 persons constituting 95.83 of the respondents responded with yes to the question of being conversant with the utilities of budget in the country. This showed that the sample group consisted of persons whose responses were quite relevant to the issue under investigation.

Interpretation of Response to Question Two

116 persons which is 96.67% of the sample affirmed that budget is a strong political instrument in the hand of the government.

Interpretation of Response to Question Three

108 persons which is 90% of the sample agreed that budget was a useful tool which the government can use for resource redistribution. This means that the instrument of budget can assist the government in correcting anomalies resulting from the application of the resource distribution that was based on revenue sharing formula.

Interpretation of Response to Question Four

32 persons consisting of 26.67% of the sample group hold the view that Nigerian governments have adequately applied budget as an instrument of resource redistribution. On the other hand 73.33% express the view that Nigerian governments have not made effective use of budget as an instrument of resource redistribution. Based on the rule of simple

percentage statistical equation, the conclusion is that Nigerian governments have not adequately utilized budget as an instrument of resource redistribution.

The summary of findings based on responses to questions in the questionnaires are:

One: budget is a political instrument which the government should apply for effective resource redistribution.

Two: the governments in Nigeria have not effectively applied budget as a tool of resource redistribution.

Three: there is an urgent need for Nigerian governments to apply budget as a tool of resource redistribution. These findings agree with and give credence to Udoh (2022); Udoh (2024) and Udoh, U S. and Madueke, O. (2018).

CONCLUSION

In addition to interpretations from respondents, the researcher deduced from observation that the country was faced with numerous agitations because the instrument of budget has not been consciously applied as a tool of resource redistribution. Rather personal and ethnic interests have guided budget making in the country.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are advanced:

1. Relevant political authorities should liaise with the originator of the theories of pawpaw and pineapple to see the extent the ideas will be further developed towards assisting in putting the instrument of budget in its proper perspective as a tool of resource redistribution.
2. Relevant governmental authorities must reduce the extent that personal and ethnic interests inform their roles in budget making.

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